

Influence of resin's chemistry on the bulk properties of CFRPs processed with recycled carbon fibres

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Knowledge for Tomorrow

Introduction

The wind energy sector – why are we talking about recycling?

Fig. 1: Some regular recycling trends for WT blades

Fig. 2: Zebra (Zero waste Blade ReseArch) Project launched in Mar 2022 and Siemens Gamesa's RecyclableBlade.

The Recycling Process

Fig. 4: Fibre surface under SEM a) Vriigin and b) in-house recycled [1].

Fig. 3: Pictorial representation of the recycling process for Elium CFRPs. Parallel strands show recovery of undamaged fibre preform (top) and the reclaimed matrix (bottom). 2nd generation CFRPs were processed with fresh Elium and the reclaimed CF preform via VARI. [1]

Evaluating the influence

Performance of recycled composites – general re-use

Common Industrial resins:

- Epoxy (dissimilar to Elium)
- Vinylester (similar to Elium)
- Urethane Acrylate (similar to Elium)

Fig. 5: EU's waste Framework directive.

Fig. 6: Comparative structural performance of 1st and 2nd generation composites wrt a) ILSS and b) Bending load [2]

[2] Gebhardt et al., Compos Comm, 2021, 28, 100974.

The Team Involved

Thank You

